

AIR POLLUTION - ITS IMPACTS ON HUMAN HEALTH

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Abstract : Air pollution is one of the biggest threats affecting all life forms including the environment. The major contribution to air pollution is introduction of harmful gases, particulates and biological molecules into the earth's atmosphere causing diseases, allergies and even death to humans. Air pollutants cause immediate health problems, including aggravated cardiovascular and respiratory illnesses, stress to heart and lungs, damaging the cells in the respiratory system and also causing harm to other living organisms and food crops .Both human activity and natural processes can cause air pollution. This paper presents the issue of air pollution and discusses the latest findings of fundamental research with regard to its consequences on human health. The nature and sources of air pollution are also discussed.

Keywords: Air pollution, Health effects, Pollutants, Prevention.

I. INTRODUCTION

Air pollution refers to the condition in which the existence of toxic substances in the atmosphere, (generated by various human activities and natural phenomena such as volcanic eruptions), pose a threat to the welfare of human beings and the living environment. This is a very serious problem which is difficult to treat due to the nature of airborne particles. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), outdoor air pollution is classified into four main categories: particulate matter, ozone, nitrogen dioxide, and sulphur dioxide. This risk is a function of the hazard of the pollutant and the exposure to that pollutant [1, 2]. In addition there are compounds (water vapour, carbon dioxide, methane, carbon monoxide, ozone, ammonia) whose concentrations vary with height. When the concentrations of the harmful gases and the particulate matter exceeds the threshold limit, it becomes a serious problem which has to be immediately addressed. Air pollution exposure can be expressed for an individual, for certain groups (e.g. neighbourhoods or children living in a country), or for entire populations (3).

II. SOURCES OF AIRPOLLUTION

There are six main categories of air pollutants recognized by the EPA (Environmental protection act) -Particulate matter, Ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulphur dioxide, carbon monoxide and lead.

2.1Particulate matter

Particulate matter is composed of many components such as acids, organic chemicals, metals, soil, wood, and dust. Particulate matter pollution is classified primarily by particle size, with smaller particles being the cause of most health problems .The types of health problems are related to the relative size of the contaminant. Usually, contaminants are inhaled through the mouth and nose, affecting primarily the trachea and lungs. Conditions such as asthma and allergies can be enhanced when faced with this class of contaminants [4, 5].

2.2Ozone

Ozone can almost be viewed as a two-edged sword. When present in the earth's upper atmosphere, this is beneficial because it protects plants and animals from the sun's harmful UV rays. However, when present at ground-level, it is damaging to these same plants and animals. Ground level ozone is created when volatile organic compounds react chemically with nitrogen oxides through complex interactions. For animals, this harmful ozone can irritate the lung airways, causing inflammation. Also, ozone can promote asthma, reduce lung capacity, and increase the chances of getting pneumonia and bronchitis. For plants, ozone increases disease and insect susceptibility as well as increasing the effects of harsh weather and other pollutants [3, 4].

2.3Nitrogen dioxide

Nitrogen dioxide is formed naturally, but is primarily produced by automobiles, electric plants, and other sources that burn fuel at high temperatures. Health problems attributed to nitrogen dioxide can include respiratory illness induced by impairment of the defence system [5]. In a laboratory test, when inhaled by mice, phagocytic activity was impaired, reducing resistance to infection through a hindered immune system [6, 7].

2.4Sulphur dioxide

Sulphur dioxide is primarily produced by coal burning utilities and off-road vehicles running on high-sulphur fuel [8]. Sulphur dioxide is a respiratory, skin, and conjunctiva irritant. When inhaled, it initiates formation of hydrogen peroxide and free oxygen radicals which can damage numerous tissues due to their high reactivity. It also affects the antioxidant ability of erythrocytes and lipid peroxidation [9, 10].

2.5 Carbon monoxide

Carbon monoxide is a colourless, odourless gas produced when fuel is not burnt completely. Vehicles are the primary producers of this contaminant. During cold months, carbon monoxide concentration is the highest due to temperature inversions, preventing the gas from dispersing. Cardiovascular and central nervous system conditions can develop when inhaled. At high concentrations, it can be lethal.

2.6 Lead

Lead is naturally found in the environment and also in manmade materials such as paint. Vehicles and factories used to be the primary sources, however, with new petroleum requirements this is not the case anymore. Lead contamination is usually present near lead smelters and battery manufacturers. Lead poisoning typically affects small children because it can settle on surfaces near the ground. High concentrations can affect all body systems and is a major problem in the environment due to biological accumulation [11].

III. Sources of air pollutants:

FIG1.SHOWS SOURCES OF AIR POLLUTION

IV. EFFECT OF AIR POLLUTION ON HEALTH

Air pollution causes premature deaths and was a significant risk factor for a number of pollution related diseases including respiratory infections, heart disease, COPD (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease), stroke and lung cancer. The health effects caused by air pollution may include difficulty in breathing, wheezing, coughing, asthma and worsening of existing respiratory and cardiac conditions. These effects can result in increased medication use, increased doctor or emergency department visits, more hospital admissions and premature deaths. Individual reactions to air pollutants depend on the type of pollutant a person is exposed to, the degree of exposure, and the individual's health status and genetics. The most common source of air pollution includes particulates, ozone, nitrogen dioxide, and sulphur dioxide. Children aged less than five years living in developing countries are the most vulnerable population in terms of total deaths attributable to indoor and outdoor air pollution.

Air pollution has serious effects on the human health. Depending on the level of exposure and the type of pollutant inhaled, these effects can vary, ranging from simple symptoms like coughing and the irritation of the respiratory tract to acute conditions like asthma and chronic lung diseases. Skin problems and irritations can develop due to prolonged exposure to several air pollutants, and a variety of cancer forms may develop after inhaling air contaminants.

Fig 2 shows Schematic drawing, causes and effects of air pollution: (1) greenhouse effect, (2) Particulate contamination (3) increased UV radiation, (4) acid rain, (5) increased ground-level ozone concentration, (6) increased levels of nitrogen oxides.

4.1 Lung disease

Research has demonstrated increased risk of developing asthma and COPD from increased exposure to traffic-related air pollution. Additionally, air pollution has been associated with increased hospitalization and mortality from asthma and COPD. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) includes diseases such as chronic bronchitis and emphysema.

More recent studies have shown that air pollution exposure from traffic reduces lung function development in children and lung function may be compromised by air pollution even at low concentrations. Air pollution exposure also cause lung cancer in non-smokers. Studies have shown that in urban areas patients suffer mucus hypersecretion, cystic fibrosis lower levels of lung function, and more self-diagnosis of chronic bronchitis and emphysema [12].

4.2 Exposure

Air pollution exposure can be expressed for an individual, for certain groups (e.g. neighbourhoods or children living in a country), or for entire populations. For example, one may want to calculate the exposure to a hazardous air pollutant for a geographic area, which includes the various microenvironments and age groups. This can be calculated as an inhalation exposure. This would account for daily exposure in various settings (e.g. different indoor micro-environments and outdoor locations). The exposure needs to include different age and other demographic groups, especially infants, children, pregnant women and other sensitive subpopulations. The exposure to an air pollutant must integrate the concentrations of the air pollutant with respect to the time spent in each setting and the respective inhalation rates for each subgroup for each specific time that the subgroup is in the setting and engaged in particular activities (playing, cooking, reading, working, spending time in traffic, etc.). For example, a small child's inhalation rate will be less than that of an adult. A child engaged in vigorous exercise will have a higher respiration rate than the same child in a sedentary activity. The daily exposure, then, needs to reflect the time spent in each micro-environmental setting and the type of activities in these settings. The air pollutant concentration in each micro activity/micro environmental setting is summed to indicate the exposure. For some pollutants such as carbon traffic related exposures may dominate total exposure despite short exposure times since high concentrations coincide with proximity to major roads or participation to (motorized) traffic [13].

4.3 Cardiovascular disease

A 2007 review of evidence found ambient air pollution exposure is a risk factor correlating with increased total mortality from cardiovascular events (range: 12% to 14% per 10 micro/m³ increase).

Air pollution is also emerging as a risk factor for stroke, particularly in developing countries where pollutant levels are highest. A 2007 study found that in women, air pollution is not associated with haemorrhagic but with ischemic stroke. Air pollution was also found to be associated with increased incidence and mortality from coronary stroke in a cohort study in 2011. Associations are believed to be causal and effects may be mediated by vasoconstriction, low-grade inflammation and other mechanisms such as autonomic nervous system.

It is believed that much like cystic fibrosis, by living in a more urban environment serious health hazards become more apparent. Studies have shown that in urban areas patients suffer mucus hypersecretion, lower levels of lung function, and more self-diagnosis of chronic bronchitis and emphysema [14].

4.4 Cancer (lung cancer)

A review of evidence regarding whether ambient air pollution exposure is a risk factor for cancer in 2007 found solid data to conclude that long-term exposure to PM_{2.5} (fine particulates) increases the overall risk of non-accidental mortality by 6% per a 10 micro/m³ increase. Exposure to PM_{2.5} was also associated with an increased risk of mortality from lung cancer (range: 15% to 21% per 10 micro/m³ increase) and total cardiovascular mortality (range: 12% to 14% per a 10 micro/m³ increase). The review further noted that living close to busy traffic appears to be associated with elevated risks of these three outcomes – increase in

lung cancer deaths, cardiovascular deaths, and overall non-accidental deaths. The reviewers also found suggestive evidence that exposure to PM_{2.5} is positively associated with mortality from coronary heart diseases and exposure to SO₂ increases mortality from lung cancer, but the data was insufficient to provide solid conclusions. Another investigation showed that higher activity level increases deposition fraction of aerosol particles in human lung and recommended avoiding heavy activities like running in outdoor space at polluted areas [15].

In 2011, a large Danish epidemiological study found an increased risk of lung cancer for patients who lived in areas with high nitrogen oxide concentrations. In this study, the association was higher for non-smokers than smokers. An additional Danish study, also in 2011, likewise noted evidence of possible associations between air pollution and other forms of cancer, including cervical cancer and brain cancer.

4.5 Effect on Children's health

In the United States, despite the passage of the Clean Air Act in 1970, in 2002 at least 146 million Americans were living in non-attainment areas—regions in which the concentration of certain air pollutants exceeded federal standards. These dangerous pollutants are known as the criteria pollutants, and include ozone, particulate matter, sulphur dioxide, nitrogen dioxide, carbon monoxide, and lead. Protective measures to ensure children's health are being taken in cities such as New Delhi, India where buses now use compressed natural gas to help eliminate the "pea-soup" smog. A recent study in Europe has found that exposure to ultrafine particles can increase blood pressure in children. According to a WHO report-2018, polluted air is a main cause poisoning millions of children under the age of 15 years and ruining their lives which resulting to death of some six hundred thousand children annually[16].

V. PREVENTION OF AIR POLLUTION

5.1 Control devices

The following items are commonly used as pollution control devices in industry and transportation. They can either destroy contaminants or remove them from an exhaust stream before it is emitted into the atmosphere.

5.2 Particulate control

Mechanical collectors (dust cyclones, multicyclones)

Electrostatic precipitators (ESP), or electrostatic air cleaner is a particulate collection device that removes particles from a flowing gas (such as air), using the force of an induced electrostatic charge. Electrostatic precipitators are highly efficient filtration devices that minimally impede the flow of gases through the device, and can easily remove fine particulates such as dust and smoke from the air stream.

Baghouses Designed to handle heavy dust loads, a dust collector consists of a blower, dust filter, a filter-cleaning system, and a dust receptacle or dust removal system (distinguished from air cleaners which utilize disposable filters to remove the dust).

Particulate scrubbers Wet scrubber is a form of pollution control technology. The term describes a variety of devices that use pollutants from a furnace flue gas or from other gas streams. In a wet scrubber, the polluted gas stream is brought into contact with the scrubbing liquid, by spraying it with the liquid, by forcing it through a pool of liquid, or by some other contact method, so as to remove the pollutants.

5.2.1 Scrubbers

5.2.2 Baffle spray scrubber

5.2.3 Cyclonic spray scrubber

5.2.4 Ejector venturi scrubber

5.2.4 Mechanically aided scrubber

5.2.5 Spray tower

5.2.6 Wet scrubber

5.3 NO_x control

Selective catalytic reduction (SCR) and selective non-catalytic reduction (SNCR) reduce post combustion NO_x by reacting the exhaust with urea or ammonia to produce nitrogen and water. SCR is now being used in ships, diesel trucks and in some diesel cars. The use of exhaust gas recirculation and catalytic converters in motor vehicle engines have significantly reduced vehicular emissions. NO_x was the main focus of the Volkswagen emissions violations.

Other technologies such as flameless oxidation (FLOX) and staged combustion significantly reduce thermal NO_x in industrial processes. Bowin low NO_x technology is a hybrid of staged-premixed-radiant combustion technology with a major surface combustion preceded by a minor radiant combustion. In the Bowin burner, air and fuel gas are premixed at a ratio greater than or equal to the stoichiometric combustion requirement. Water Injection technology, whereby water is introduced into the combustion chamber, is also becoming an important means of NO_x reduction through increased efficiency in the overall combustion process. Alternatively, the water (e.g. 10 to 50%) is emulsified into the fuel oil before the injection and combustion. This emulsification can either be made in-line (unstabilized) just before the injection or as a drop-in fuel with chemical additives for long term emulsion stability (stabilized). Inline emulsified fuel/water mixtures show NO_x reductions between 4 and 83%.

VI. CONCLUSION

While one debate all day about specific levels or exact factors actually harming our health, we seem to know on a general level that air pollution just isn't a good thing to have around. Science is constantly evolving, and we are learning more every day about the hazards of pollution and the role that the environment has on our health. Recently, new reports on air pollution and disease have surfaced, providing more evidence that air quality may affect us even more than we thought. While more research is needed

to ascertain the particular contributing factors, we have long known that diesel pollution, commonly found in the air near freeways, has been found to be harmful to human health. The trigger by which traffic-related air pollution affects respiratory and cardiovascular disease, and perhaps autism, is through inflammation and oxidative stress. Given that it has been estimated that 11 percent of the U.S. population lives within 100 meters of a four-lane highway, the implications for public health are far-reaching. Environmental factors like poor air quality need more attention – especially in Texas[18]. We need more study, more monitoring, more discussion and more public awareness. Our health continues to be at risk otherwise.

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